

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st December 2022

Accepted: 12th December 2022

Online: 13th December 2022

KEY WORDS

Speech behavior, gender, male speech, female speech, genderlect, language variability, gender differences in speech behavior, style, style of communication.

GENDER ELEMENT OF SPEECH BEHAVIOR FROM THE POSITION OF TEXT ORGANIZATION MECHANISMS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7432827>

ABSTRACT

This article describes the features of speech behavior in the framework of the sociolinguistic approach. One of its key concepts is sexual selection (linguistic diversity by gender). Sociolinguistics considers gender as a socio-demographic characteristic that determines linguistic diversity along with occupation, age, and social origin. Gender is fundamentally different from biological and grammatical gender. It is constructed by society, not established by nature. This study analyzes the lexical and grammatical features that allow women and men to talk about their communication styles. In conclusion, it is concluded that the features of male and female oral and written statements, the composition of the text indicate the presence of gender differences in speech behavior, which requires a more detailed and detailed consideration.

Introduction: Achievements in the field of the latest linguistic research clearly indicate the significant interest and desire of linguists to study linguistic phenomena in a broad extralinguistic context. This trend is probably due to the intensification of international contacts and how, consequently, a kind of "language boom", that is, the awareness by an increasing number of people of the need to learn a foreign language as a means of intercultural communication. It, in turn, leads to the need to master not only the basic levels and categories of the language, but also the peculiar information reflected in the language, which is dictated by the

desire to avoid disharmony in the communication of speakers of different cultures, which can manifest itself as a socio-cultural imbalance, non-identity of subjective pictures of the world or worldview conflict, inadequate perception of the speech genre, inconsistency of role expectations and prescriptions, etc.

The attitude of modern linguistics to the study of the human factor in language and the formation of an integrated interdisciplinary approach to linguistic research is reflected in the synthesizing linguocultural and sociolinguistic approach to the description of the lexical level of a language that we have proposed. In the

dissertation, using this approach, an attempt is made to linguoculturological analysis of gender stereotypes reflected in the lexical and phraseological composition of the modern English language.

Methods and materials

Modern studies of speech behavior are carried out within the framework of sociolinguistics, where gender is one of the socio-demographic features that determine the variability of the language along with profession, age, and social origin.

It is from sociolinguistics that the term genderlect was taken, which denotes the gender-based variability of language. Gender is fundamentally different from biological sex or grammatical gender. It is not set by nature, but is constructed by society.

How does society see the female and male genderlects? What are the differences between male and female speech styles?

Men are more categorical. Men's sentences are usually shorter than women's ones. Women's speech includes a large amount of evaluative vocabulary. Women tend to increase their positive assessment, while men quite often use a negative one, they use slang words and expressions much more often.

Exaggerated expressiveness is a typical feature of female speech. Women's speech is much more emotional in relation to a partner. This is expressed in the frequent use of interjections, metaphors, comparisons, epithets, diminutive forms of words. Women have a more polite nature of remarks, although more assertive speech behavior, women are more inclined to make demands presented in the form of requests.

Women's speech is more conservative (it is no coincidence that dialectologists tend to

observe women's speech). Men are more receptive to new things in the language: there are more neologisms and terms in their speech.

Women are more careful in offers, statements, demands. So, they use modifiers: "I'm not sure", "maybe". Statements often remain unspecified: for example, sentences with the words "perhaps", "something", "approximately" are frequent.

In addition to lexical and grammatical features that allow us to talk about male and female communication styles, there are language differences at a higher level - textual. Men and women construct statements differently. The subject of the text, its problems and means of expression, the syntactic construction of sentences, vocabulary may indicate gender differences. In order to confirm this, we will cite two stories - a story told by a man and a story told by a woman. The first one was written by Alexey Belyakov, the second one belongs to Elena Gladskikh. The story told by a man is called "Men have forgotten how to be silent. At all". "It was a long time ago. I came to visit a friend. We sit in the kitchen, we have a cultural conversation. His wife appears. Starts screaming. Not that on business, but just like that, the mood is bad. A moment of silliness. She doesn't like it, and that's what she's unhappy with. I would have been furious for a long time and barked back. A friend sits, smokes, is silent. The wife screams. The friend is silent. "Can you hear me?" - the wife is indignant. The friend nods. But he is silent. Wife got tired, went away. A friend asks, "So what were we talking about? About Borges? And he continues the conversation, as if nothing had happened.

The main character is the narrator himself or the narrator together with friends. In the center of the story are conflicts between people: clashes of worldviews, life positions. Most often, the conflict is ideological or principled.

As a rule, from any difficult situation, the male narrator (alone or together with friends, if they acted "at the same time") comes out the winner. The end of the story contains the results of personal experience, morality. The narrator's remarks tend to turn into generalizations.

Men's stories rarely contain everyday details, details, if they do not have a significant impact on the course of events. The narrator rarely talks about his personal problems, reluctantly about feelings, almost never about fears and doubts.

From a linguistic point of view. Tendency to "careless" style of presentation of events. Sometimes it seems that the narrator did not intend to speak, but decided to speak out, since the listeners or the situation require it. The negligence of style, the utmost conciseness is achieved through the use of inversion (there was a case, I arrived), one-part (we sit, talk, start screaming, a minute of nonsense) and uncommon sentences, parceling (His wife appears. Starts screaming. Not really on business, but just).

The lexical side of the text also gives the impression of carelessness, achieved through a combination of colloquial (barked, gets more excited, unwinds) and book vocabulary (fruitful dialogue, on the verge of decay, virtue, eloquent). In addition, the lexical appearance of the text indicates an ironic attitude to the situation. The weightiness of the author's conclusions is also emphasized by the use

of expressive and visual means of the language - set expressions (to spill like a nightingale) and gradation (stupidity, husk, garbage).

The stories women tell are different. The choice of topic, the placement of accents, the means of expression used will be different.

As an example, the story of Elena Gladsky called "Twos and Love": how to be a teacher.

"Yesterday, for the first time, I did not regret that I came to the parent meeting.

It all started as usual: "make sure that the girls' hair is in a ponytail", "take the exam soon", "our lyceum is in the TOP-10, and we must comply ..." But then an elderly math teacher appeared on a cloudy day with an unexpected sun. The algebra textbook in her hands was wrapped in a bright red dog, and geometry in a peach cat.

"Dear parents," she said. "I really want to teach your children math, but I can't do without your help. Children should come to me well-fed, well-rested and in a good mood, otherwise I will have no one to go to science with.

The heroine of this story is not a direct participant in the events. Rather, she plays the role of an observer, telling about what is happening. Women's stories are generally characterized by the presence of a large number of characters, a description of their positions and behavior. The narrator does not confine himself to retelling the situation, but tries to penetrate the inner world of the characters, to give comments.

Results and discussion

Speaking about the results of my research in this article, I would like to highlight the following theses, which fully reflect them:

1. The use of the field method to describe the mutual influence of linguistic and sociocultural phenomena seems to be the most effective. The characteristic features of the field are: the semantic commonality of the elements, the presence of homogeneous and heterogeneous elements, the systemic nature of the relations of the field elements, the division into microfields, the dynamism of the field, the presence of a core and periphery, the openness of the field.

2. The linguoculturological field, as an important factor in the study of the lexico-semantic features of units of language and culture as a whole, is characterized by the two-dimensionality of the semantics of the linguocultures included in it, representing the unity of linguistic meaning and extralinguistic meaning, indicating the socio-cultural characteristics of the nation.

3. The linguoculturological field "Man and woman (in society and family)", characterized by the presence of synonymous and antonymic semantic connections, consists of five interacting lexico-phraseosemantic microfields: "Men and women", "Gender problems and feminism", "Love", "Sex", "Family". The latter occupies a leading position in terms of the volume of language material (38%), thereby confirming the value of family relations and the importance of the family institution for the English-speaking society.

4. Gender markers of the structure of language units are represented by anthropometric vocabulary (53.8%), kinship terms (28.7%) and anthroponymic lexemes (17.5%).

5. The linguistic cultural field "Man and woman (in society and family)" is characterized by the predominance of feminine vocabulary (ratio 1.9: 1), which,

firstly, is associated with the multifunctional and significant role of women (especially in the family), and, secondly, with the phenomenon of gender conceptual and lexical lacunarity, based on the ability: childbearing and the leading role of women in raising children.

6. In the gender picture of the world of the English-speaking society, the image of a man is formed due to the concepts - "masculinity", "career", "provided life", "passion for women", "polygamy", "paternity", "equal spouse"; the female image is prescribed concepts - "socio-biological functions of a woman", "sexually attractive appearance", "age", "love", "marriage", "ideal wife", "motherhood", "hostess", "close friend", "independent woman", "equal partner".

7. The influence of the gender component on the formation of appraisal is observed: for a woman, almost any comparison with a man is positive, and the use of words denoting women in relation to a man carries a clearly negative charge.

8. A feminist movement that has made significant changes to the marriage union of a man and a woman and to the traditional distribution of gender social roles. reduced the androcentricity of the English language, and also intensified the process of neologization within the framework of the socio-cultural process of political correctness. There is a trend towards an increase in the frequency of describing a woman as self-confident, successful, etc.; the modern English family acts as a married family, a union of equal partners; the image of a man changes to the image of a caring and helping husband around the house and a father who is actively involved in raising children. The main ways of forming neologisms in

modern English are: word formation, change in meaning, affixation, fusion.

Conclusion

Unlike the men's, the women's story contains many details and details: starting with a list of issues discussed at the parent meeting, and ending with a description of the covers in which the math teacher's books were wrapped. The use of direct speech testifies to the attentive attitude to the thoughts and feelings of the heroes of history, the desire to retell them to the maximum extent and with minimal distortion. Complex sentences, sentences with homogeneous members give the impression of a smooth, measured narrative. Especially in comparison with short, weighty phrases of men's history.

The narrator is interested in the feelings of the characters. This is confirmed by the use of evaluative vocabulary (honey),

evaluative figurative means (metaphor "the sun on a cloudy day"), words and phrases that convey the emotional state of a person (disappointed, saddened, timidly asked, sadly, sincerely, without mood, touched, adores, tired handkerchief).

The narrative ends with the phrase: "Tomorrow I'll bake her a cake." The author does not assess the situation directly, verbally, does not seek to convince the reader. However, the final words of the story become a full-fledged conclusion, allowing you to understand the narrator's attitude to what is happening, his emotional state and even his life position.

In conclusion, I would like to note that my analysis, statements and conclusions do not claim to be complete and are not exhaustive, they only indicate the presence of gender differences in speech behavior that require further research.

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